

THE ANALYSIS OF THE AREAS OF POPULATION GROWTH OF KASHKADARYA REGION

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Key words: Kashkadarya demography, population density, migration, life expectancy, birth, natural change, natural increase, permanent population, national structure.

Annotation: In this article, socio-economic, demographic factors, oasis demography, population growth from other regions of the republic in Kashkadarya region for the years 1991-2021, decrease in birth rate and birth rate, changes in population density and location, increase in average life expectancy, growth of urban population in rural areas issues of slowing down of population, activation of migration are analyzed on the basis of archival sources and statistical data.

In 1999, the population of Kashkadarya region was 2166.3 thousand people, of which 1061.5 thousand men and 1104.8 thousand women [1:1492-1495]. Out of that, the urban population was 553.1 thousand people, 265.5 thousand men, 287.6 thousand women, 1613.2 thousand rural residents, 790.4 thousand men, 822.8 thousand women. By the year 2000, there were 2,212,7 people, of which 1,084,2 were men, 1,128,5 were women, of which the population of the city was 561,7, of which 269,6 were men, 292,292 were women. 1 thousand people, the population of the village is 1651.0 thousand people, men 807.3 thousand people. There were 843,7 people. In 2001, there were 2294.7 thousand people, of which 1104.3 thousand were men and 1149.4 thousand were women. Out of that, the urban population was 563,7 people, 270,6 men, 293,100 women, 1690,000 rural people, 828,1, 861,9 women. In 2002, the population was 2294.7 thousand people, of which 1148.9 thousand men and 1145.8 thousand women. Out of this, the urban population is 572.5 thousand, men are 286.9 thousand, women are 285.6 thousand, rural population is 1722.2 thousand, men are 862 thousand, women are 860.2 thousand.

According to the national composition of the population in the region in 1999, there were 1958, 3000 Uzbeks, 2,000 Kazakhs, 122,9000 Tajiks, 0.3000 Kyrgyz, 26,8000Turkmens, 22,8000 Russians, and 33,2000 other nationalities organized.

In 2000, there were 2000.3 thousand Uzbeks, 2.0 thousand Kazakhs, 125.5 thousand Tajiks, 0.3 thousand Kyrgyz, 27.4 thousand Turkmens, 23.3 thousand Russians, and 33.9 thousand other nationalities. In 2002, there were 2129.5 thousand Uzbeks, 1.9 thousand Kazakhs, 107.4 thousand Tajiks, 0.2 thousand Kyrgyz, 27.9

thousand Turkmens, 24.1 thousand Russians, and 42.2 thousand other nationalities. In 1999, there were 75.8 thousand people per 1 sq.km of the province, while in 2002, 80.1 thousand people lived there. So, the population is getting denser year by year.

In 1999, the number of births in the region was 59,573, of which the number of deaths was 9,316, and the natural increase was 50,257. In 2002, there were 54,371 people [2:135-138], the number of deaths was 9,917 people, and the natural increase was 44,909 people.

Natural population change was 27.5 per thousand in 1999 and 23.9 per thousand in 2002. The death rate was 4.3 per thousand in 1999 and 4.4 per thousand in 2002. Natural growth was 23.2 per thousand in 1999 and 19.5 per thousand in 2002 [15].

As of January 1, 2008, the population of Kashkadarya region was 2 million 506.2 thousand, of which 613.8 thousand were urban, 1 million 892.4 thousand were rural. Chirakchi district has the largest population of 302,100 people (20,600 urban residents, 281,500 rural residents). There are 288,900 people in Shahrisabz district (out of which, the population of the city [3:1-6] was 100,6 people, and the population of the village was 188,3 people). The population of Dehkanabad district, which is the largest in terms of territory, is 112,400 people, of which 9,300 urban residents and 103,100 rural residents.

It can be seen that the majority of the population in Dehqonabad district lived in villages. 145,800 people lived in Kasbi district, 89,600 people lived in Mirishkor district, and all residents of both districts lived in villages. Among the districts, Mubarak district has the smallest population of 67,100 people, of which 24,700 urban residents and 42,400 rural residents. The population of the opposite city was 228,2 thousand people.

Among the districts that occupy one of the main places economically, the population of Koson district is 215,4000 people, the urban population is 60,300 people, and the rural population is 155,100 people. In 2004, the population of the region was 2 million 378.2 thousand people, in 2005 it was 2 million 419.8 thousand people, in 2006 it was 2 million 462.2 thousand people [4:96-100], of which men in 2004 were 1 million, 191.2 thousand people, women 1 million 187.0 thousand people, in 2005 1 million 211.8 thousand people, women 1 million 208.0 thousand people, in 2006 1 million 233.2 thousand people, women 1 million 229, 0 thousand people [15].

Also, in 2004, the urban population was 587.5 thousand people, the rural population was 1 million 790.7 thousand people, of which 294.0 thousand men lived in

the city, 897.2 thousand people lived in the village, and 293.3 thousand urban women. if he did, the number of women living in the village was 893,500.

In 2006, the urban population was 606.7 thousand people, the rural population was 1 million 855.5 thousand people, of which 303.5 thousand men lived in the city, and 929.7 thousand people lived in the village.], the number of women living in rural areas was 925,8 thousand.

According to the national composition of the population in 2004, the number of Uzbeks in the region was 2 million 170.3 thousand, Tajiks 111.2 thousand, Turkmen 29.0 thousand, Russians 23.9 thousand, Tatars 10.0 thousand, Kazakhs 1.9 thousand, Koreans 1.3 thousand, Kyrgyz 0.2 thousand, other [6:128-131] nationalities made up 30.4 thousand. In 2006, the number of Uzbeks in the region was 2 million 251.5 thousand, Tajiks 113.9 thousand, Turkmen 30.0 thousand, Russians 23.1 thousand, Tatars 9.7 thousand, Kazakhs 2.0 thousand, Koreans 1.2 thousand, Kyrgyz 0. 2 thousand other nationalities made up 30.6 thousand. It can be seen that during 2004-2006, the number of Uzbeks, Kazakhs, Tajiks, and Turkmens increased, while the number of Russians, Tatars, and Koreans decreased. The main reason for this is related to their birth and migration processes.

According to the natural population change, in 2004, 53,239 people were born in the region, 9,294 people died, in 2006, 53,731 people were born and 10,019 people died. Natural population change: births in 2004 were 22.6 per thousand in 2006, 22.0 per thousand in 2006, death was 3.9 per thousand in 2006, 4.1 per thousand in 2006. Natural increase was 18.7 ppm, in 2006 it was 17.9 ppm.

The population of Kashkadarya region in 2011 was 2 million 777.8 people, of which 1390.8 thousand men and 1387.0 thousand women. The urban population is 1203.9, men are 602.7 thousand, women are 601.2 thousand [7:128-132], the rural population is 1573.9 thousand, of which men are 788.1 thousand, women are 785, There were 8 thousand people.

In 2014, the population of the region was 2960.6 thousand people, of which 1487.7 thousand men and 1472.9 thousand women. The population of the city is 1275.2, men are 641.4 thousand, women are 633.8 thousand, rural population is 1685.4 thousand, of which men are 846.3 thousand and women are 839.1 thousand.

According to the national composition of the region's population in 2011, there were 2560.6 thousand Uzbeks, 120.4 thousand Tajiks, 32.1 thousand Turkmens, 21.4 thousand Russians, 9.1 thousand Tatars, others [8:73-76] nations made up 34.2 thousand people. In 2014, the national composition of the population was Uzbeks

2,675,900, Tajiks 122,400, Turkmens 32,600, Russians 21,100, Tatars 8,700, and other nationalities 34,600.

2015 analysis of the population of regional districts 185,300 people in Guzor district[9] the city population was 43.7 thousand people, the rural population was 141.6 thousand people. In Dehkhanaabad District, there are 131,700 people, 25,200 urban residents, 106,500 rural residents. Qamashi District has 243,200 people, 57,400 urban residents and 185,800 rural residents. The population of Karshi District is 220,700, the urban population is 80,900, and the rural population is 139,800.

In Koson District, there are 255,400 people, 132,300 urban residents and 123,100 rural residents. The permanent population of Kitab District is 239,100 people, 89,800 urban residents and 149,300 rural residents. The number of permanent [10:59-63] residents of Mirishkor District is 108,600 people, of which 40,400 are urban residents, 68.2 thousand are rural residents.

The number of permanent residents of Mubarak District is 79,200 people, of which 62,600 are urban residents and 16,600 are urban residents. The number of permanent residents [11:73-76] in Nishan District is 134,000 people, of which 81,300 are urban residents, 52.7 thousand are rural residents. The permanent resident population of Kasbi District is 177,700[12:86-90], of which 68,100 and 109,600 are urban residents.

The number of permanent residents of Chirakchi District is 360,300 people, of which 87,200 are urban residents, 273,100 are rural residents.

330,800 people in Shahrisabz district, of which urban population was 171.6 thousand people, rural population was 159.2 thousand people. The number of permanent residents of Yakkabog District is 236,400 people, of which 76,500 are urban residents and 159,900 rural residents. The number of permanent residents in Karshi[13:386-391] was 258,200 people. The permanent population of the region is 2 million 960.6 thousand people, the urban population is 1275.2 thousand people, the rural population is 1685.4 thousand people.

Natural population change In 2011, 64,037 people were born, 10,904 people died, natural growth was 53,133 people. In 2012, 64,272 people were born [14:292-296] and 10,863 people died, the natural increase was 53,409 people. In 2014, 77,493 people were born and 12,063 people died, the natural increase was 65,430 people.

The natural population growth in 2011 was 23.3 per thousand births, 4.0 per thousand deaths, and 19.3 per thousand births. In 2014, the birth rate was 26.5 per thousand, the death rate was 4.1 per thousand, and the natural increase was 22.3 per thousand. So, in the period of 1991-2021 in the Kashkadarya region, socio-economic

and demographic factors play an important role, the demography of the oasis is different from other regions of the republic, the growth of the population, the decrease in birth and death rates, changes in the population density and location, the increase in the average life expectancy, the city population growth is explained by the slowing down of the rural population, the activation of migration.

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